

In memoriam

ACADEMICIAN, PROF. DR. DUŠAN ČAMPRAK

(1925-2021)

Academician Dr. Dušan Čamprag, retired full professor of entomology at the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, passed away on March 22, 2021. With his passing, the scientific and professional communities lost one of the pioneers of plant protection in our country, a well-known entomologist and the oldest member of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts (SASA).

Prof. Dr. Dušan Čamprag was born on March 14, 1925 in Ada. He finished elementary and high school in Novi Sad. He took part in the National Liberation War and was a war invalid after being wounded in the spring of 1945. He graduated from the Faculty of Agriculture in Belgrade in 1951 and then completed a one-year specialization in the field of plant protection at the Provincial Institute for Agricultural Research in Novi Sad. His first years of service (1952-1956) were at the Institute for Sugar Beet in Crvenka.

In 1957, at the Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad, he was engaged as an assistant in the subject of Agricultural Entomology and became an associate of academician Pavle Vukasović. At the same faculty, in 1961, he defended his doctoral dissertation entitled "Snout beetles (Curculionidae) as a pest of sugar beet in Bačka with special reference to *Bothynoderes punctiventris* Germ., *Lixus scabricollis* Boh. and some others", which was soon after published as separately as a book. He then passed through all academic steps, from assistant professor (1962) to full professor (1975), working until the end of 1982, when he retired on a disability pension.

Dr. Čamprag was one of the founders of the Department and the Institute for Plant Protection of the Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad. As a teacher, he participated in the education of plant protection experts (today phytomedicine) for over a quarter of a century, lecturing in Special Entomology and Forecasting in Plant Protection, while he taught the subject Protection of Field Crops (zoological part) to students of the study program for cultivation of field and vegetable crops. With academician Vukasović, he participated in the editing and writing of the textbook "Pests in Plant Production", parts I and II (1964, 1967), along with numerous other authors from all over the former Yugoslavia. He was an excellent lecturer, and generations of students attended his lectures with great interest in the scientific, professional and life-experience insights that he imparted. As a mentor or member of these defense committees for specialist papers, master's theses and doctoral dissertations, he contributed to the development of many younger associates in the Institute, as well scientists in other institutions.

Professor Čamprag's field of research encompassed agricultural entomology and plant protection (especially integral plant protection). He was engaged in scientific work for around 60 years (1951-2010), mainly studying the harmful insects found on the Pannonian Plain and in southeast Europe and common to the former Yugoslavia (mainly Serbia) and three neighboring countries (Hungary, Romania and Bulgaria), as well as invasive species that appeared. Thanks to his dedication to scientific work and his intellect, he had an enviable academic output, publishing a total of 60 important scientific publications, 184 scientific papers and over 1150 professional papers, popular science articles and various reviews.

Out of 60 special editions (monographs, textbooks, atlases, manuals, brochures and chapters in books), he was the sole author of about one third, and in most of the others he was the first author. A list of significant publications and scientific papers is given at the end.

Of the total number of scientific papers, he authored about 20% alone, and was first author in almost 60% of joint papers. According to the variety of issues he studied, the published works can be classified into three groups. The first group, with almost 100 papers, involved the study of the biology, ecology, harmfulness, prognosis and integral control of important harmful insects on field crops. In them, the following species were primarily studied: *Agriotes ustulatus* Schall., *Agrotis segetum* Schiff., *Bothynoderes punctiventris* Germ., *Aphis fabae* Scop., *Mamestra brassicae* L., *Scrobipalpa ocellatella* Boyd., *Pemphigus fuscicornis* Koch, *Lygus rugulipennis* Popp., *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* Le Conte and *Helicoverpa armigera* Hbn. Particularly important are the works in which the results of long-term monitoring of the fluctuation in numbers of harmful insects depending on climatic factors, agrotechnical measures and the activity of predators are presented.

The second group includes about 60 papers related to the study of various aspects of harmful entomofauna on the main field plants, primarily sugar beet and corn, but also on sunflower, wheat, soybeans, hemp and other plants, as well as on pastures. In this group of papers, the qualitative and quantitative composition of entomofauna, the movement of the number of individual harmful species and their economic significance

were studied. The third group includes other works (about 20), written during his time at the Institute for Sugar Beet in Crvenka.

Prof. Čamprag was one of the main initiators and organizers of four international symposia on sugar beet protection held at the Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad (1964, 1966, 1969 and 2005), the First Yugoslav Symposium on Corn Protection (Novi Sad, 1968), the First Yugoslav Scientific Conference on corn rootworm, *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* Le Conte (Novi Sad, 1998), as well as 25 seminars on plant protection in Vojvodina (1977-2009).

During his working life, he made short study trips to most European countries and the USA. The longest time was spent in the former Soviet Union (three months, 1964) in the Laboratory of Soil Zoology of the Institute of Animal Morphology in Moscow, which was headed by the eminent academician M.S. Giljarov. Probably this visit encouraged him the most to study soil entomofauna, about which he wrote a significant number of scientific and professional papers. It can be said that, together with Prof. Jelena Đurkić, he founded the so-called Novi Sad schools of soil entomofauna. Thanks to this, there is detailed knowledge of insect fauna, especially from the families Elateridae and Scarabaeidae, in different soil types on the territory of the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina after the growing of small grains, sugar beet and other field plants.

Prof. Čamprag's commitment to his profession is also shown by the fact that throughout his working life he cooperated with several sugar factories, agricultural-industrial plants and agricultural services. He participated in dozens of domestic conferences where he presented the results of his own research, as well as recent knowledge on plant protection, all with the aim of educating agricultural experts and improving the protection of field crops from pests. Under his editorship, in 1977 a study was carried out on the organization and tasks of the Service for Plant Protection in Vojvodina, which he then managed for two years. He was also editor of the publication "Manual of the Forecasting and Reporting Service for the Protection of Agricultural Crops" (Belgrade, 1983), an excellent work on plant protection of about 700 pages, prepared with the participation of several scientists from all republics of the former Yugoslavia.

Professor Čamprag's contribution to the implementation of integral protection of field plants is highly significant, in the scope of which he always emphasized the importance of agrotechnical measures and prognosis in the control of harmful insects, with the aim of minimizing the use of pesticides. His work was of great importance and influence on the practice of pest control in agriculture. In cooperation with co-authors, he provided forecasts of the occurrence of root crop pests in the area of Vojvodina in approaching vegetation seasons (1961-1992), on the basis of which adequate measures were taken to reduce their populations and thus lessen the damage to field crops.

He cooperated with colleagues from the Faculty of Agriculture in Zemun, with colleagues from the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad, but also with those from the entire former Yugoslavia. He also had very good cooperation with entomologists in Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Russia, Ukraine, but also Italy and other countries in Europe and the world. This, in the time before digital technology, enabled a significant exchange of the latest literature in the field of plant protection, as well as the exchange of experts between our teaching and scientific institution and others in the country and abroad.

Prof. Čamprag held a number of managerial and sociopolitical posts during his working life: he was head of the Department of Plant Protection, director of the Institute of Plant Protection of the Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad (1977-1978), member of the Educational and Cultural Council of the Provincial Assembly of Vojvodina (1963-1966), member of the Council for Agricultural Sciences of the Federal Council for the Coordination of Scientific Research (1963-1965), member of the Managing Board of Matica Srpska (1979-1983) and president of the Association of Plant Protection Societies of Yugoslavia (1987-1990).

He was a member of the Society for Plant Protection of Serbia and the Entomological Society of Serbia, an honorary member of the Association of Agricultural Engineers and Technicians of Serbia, an honorary

member of the Hungarian Entomological Society and an honorary doctor of the Pannonian University of Agriculture in Keszthely (Hungary). He was elected a corresponding member of the Vojvodina Academy of Sciences and Arts in 1979, and a full member in 1987. He became a regular member of the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts in 1991, and in 2004 he was elected a foreign member of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences. In the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts (SASA), he participated in the work of the Department of Chemical and Biological Sciences, he was a member of the SASA Board for the Study of Serbian Fauna, and in the SASA Branch in Novi Sad he was a member of the Branch Executive Board and President of the Publishing Committee.

Upon retirement, the scientific activity of Prof. Čamprag did not stop. In fact, he wrote most of the monographs and other special publications after retirement because he had enough time for it then. He continued to apply his rich experience in research work on entomological topics as an associate of his former home institution. He was a great admirer of tradition, so on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the Department of Phytomedicine and Environmental Protection of the Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad, on his initiative and under his leadership, a monograph entitled "50 years (1960-2010) of University Education, Science and Professional Activities in the Field of Plant Protection – Phytomedicine" (Novi Sad, 2010) was published.

He was a member of the editorial board of the journal "Šećerna repa", an advocate and one of the initiators of the re-publication of the magazine "Biljni lekar", then its editor-in-chief (1995-1996), and later an active regular and honorary member of the editorial board. Unfortunately, in 2012, he had to withdraw from public duties because of ill health.

For his prolific scientific and pedagogical work, he won several recognitions and awards: the Order of Labor with a Golden Wreath (1965), the October Award of Novi Sad (1974), Diplomas with Medal given to collaborators of Matica Srpska (1976), the Liberation of Vojvodina Award (1978), Charter of the City of Novi Sad (1979), Charter of the Association of Plant Protection Societies of Yugoslavia (1983), Medals of the Sugar Factory of Županja (1987), Charter of the Sugar Factory in Crvenka for his contribution to the development of the science of sugar beet protection (1997), Golden Plaques for Lifetime Achievement from the Association of University Teachers and Scientists of Vojvodina (1998), the Charter of the Plant Protection Society of Serbia (2004) and a Certificate of Appreciation of the Entomological Society of Serbia (2008).

Professor Dušan Čamprag was blessed with the best of human qualities: honesty, truthfulness, kindness, purity of spirit and the gift of eloquence. He read a lot and passed on his knowledge with ease. He was never overassertive, nor self-congratulatory; on the contrary, he was quiet, unobtrusive and modest. He had a high moral code and was a cultured man in the broadest sense of the word. He loved theatrical performances, especially operas, and at one time, while staying on the Adriatic, he drew beautiful graphics with coastal motifs.

Having in mind Prof. Čamprag's contribution to our profession and science, much of which has not been mentioned, he occupied one of the most eminent places in phytomedicine in our country and beyond, to the pride of his family and the generations he educated. The works he left behind will live on as a guide for generations to come. His departure is a great loss for Serbia and world agronomic science. We were lucky to have worked with a man of his calibre. He will be remembered and honored.

May he rest in peace.

Tatjana Kereši and Radosav Sekulić
Professors of the Faculty of Agriculture
University of Novi Sad

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